

WAYS TO USE THE EXPERIENCE OF ADVANCED FOREIGN COUNTRIES IN IMPROVING THE BUDGET SYSTEM (USING THE EXAMPLE OF BUDGETS OF THE BUDGET SYSTEM)

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Abstract. In the middle of the XX century it was found that due to problems with the using of budget funds, western countries of the world were forced back to introduce into the budget process new management technologies aimed at qualitative transformations in the field of budget policy, such as, the program-target method. It was explored the order of application of the program-target method in foreign countries. As the practice shows, today there is no better method for the formation, implementation, monitoring and control of budget execution, and for assessing the effectiveness of budget programs. It was investigated that application of the program-target method enables to predict the results of each budget program implementation, as well as to evaluate the efficiency of the using of public funds at each stage. The proposed proposals for the application of the program-target method in Uzbekistan will facilitate the transition from the practice of using of budget funds to planning and evaluating the final results, and increasing the responsibility for implementing budget programs.

Key words: budget policy, budget process, foreign experience, new managerial technologies, program- target method, medium-term budget planning, strategic planning.

The main idea of using the proposed method of predicting is that the planning of indicators begins with the calculation of prediction indicators for the planned and the next two planned budget periods. Based on the estimated values, the budget for the next budget period is approved, and the prediction of individual indicators of social

and economic development of the country of the other two years becomes the basis for the development of budgets of the following periods. At the same time, approval of each next budget is necessarily accompanied by a review and correction of the prediction calculations of the third (last) period in accordance with the actual performance of the previous budget plan and the achievement of the calculated macroeconomic indicators. International experience shows that this technique significantly improves the quality of the budget planning.

1.1-figure. Medium-term budget planning based on the method of the prediction «moving average».

The Government approved the main directions of budget policy for 2018 - 2020 (so-called the budget resolution) [9]. For the first time in the history of budgeting in Uzbekistan, medium-term budget planning will be introduced.

The approved budget resolution is a strategic document that defines the direction of public finances for priority reforms. This will put in place a plan for the country's economic development in the future and create the basis for systematic deep reforms. The transition from a one-year to three-year perspective of budget planning is not just a technical change in budget formation by adding two more budget periods in the calculations. This is a systemic change in budget policy that should provide a strategic approach to identifying priority measures and an efficient allocation of the resources.

The foreign experience of using budgeting as one of the technologies of public finance management suggests that it alone cannot exist without a systematic approach, since it focuses on certain results from the using of budget funds. In turn, the effective result is virtually impossible to achieve solely due to budgeting technologies, since these are interrelated measures, and finances only serve their implementation. That is why in most foreign countries, budgeting technology was introduced at the same time as structural changes, or immediately after their implementation. And first and foremost, the whole system of public administration was reformed in order to increase the responsibility of government institutions for the results of its activities (Australia, New Zealand, Great Britain, the United States, etc.).

The methods (The technologies) of budget management in foreign countries have recently evolved quite rapidly: from the traditional budget, the budget from results (implementation), basic budgeting, budgeting on a zero basis, budgeting «sunset» to the budget based on targeted programs (priorities). All innovations after the traditional budget (cost or item) are considered as components of the program-target method of budgeting [10].

The countries of the European Union have moved on to develop an annual budgetary process, taking into account the strategic multi-year approach since the second half of the twentieth century. A common approach to long-term budgeting is the inclusion of projected estimates of profits and expenditures for several years ahead after the current year.

The program-based budgeting method at the state level was first used in the United States to develop the Ministry of Defense estimates. The practice of using this method indicates its advantages compared with other methods used in the process of drafting budgets. This contributed to the application of the program-target method of budget planning in world practice.

In the United States, the program-target budget planning method is applied both at the state budget level and at the state and state budgets of states and territories.

Budget planning with application of the program-target method in this country is longer than in other countries of the world.

Canada and most European Union countries are actively practicing the program-targeted budget method. A positive step towards improving the budget process of the EU was the introduction of 2003 at the EU level for the medium-term budget plan in the course of elaboration, adoption and implementation of the budget. This method provided an opportunity for the development and implementation of budget programs beyond the boundaries of the year, and also suggested planning of costs based on the distribution of existing commitments. Today, most EU countries provide assistance to other countries in the form of programs, after which the EU seeks to achieve real results.

According to scientists' opinion, the most progressive in terms of application of the program-target budgeting method is Australia and New Zealand [1]. Regular budget reports issued by these two countries show that they have reached a spectacular level of openness and transparency in the activities of government structures and the results that are being achieved. It is their experience of applying the program-target budgeting method, which is based on a completely new budget philosophy for Uzbekistan, is often put forward as an example to follow the other countries of the world.

In Ireland, budget calculations predict resource requirements for three to four years ahead. The horizons of these predictions are removed annually, which is a means of medium-term management of the economy and budget. In the Netherlands, predictions are for the next budget year and the next four years, and each change in budget trends leads to an appropriate correction of the whole range of five-year assessments. In Portugal, a list of programs and projects are funded under a separate approved plan of investments and expenditures, designed for four years.

In Spain, the budget process allows multi-year budgets to analyze macroeconomic and financial performance of public sector activities within a four-year period.

The experience of introducing medium-term budget planning in Sweden is rather

interesting. An important step in the budget reform carried out in the country in the late 1990s was the introduction of medium-term budget planning and the application of a new approach to the formation of the state budget «top-down». Sweden uses long-term budget planning as a basis for the annual budget process. A three-year budget cycle is established and, moreover, they develop four-year predictions of revenues, expenditures and the balance of the state budget in order to predict the results of the decisions and financial obligations.

The Government of Turkey prefers the annual budget, but its parameters depend on the target indicators of the five-year plans for socio-economic development of the country, which are mandatory for the public sector and recommended for the private sector.

It is actually for Uzbekistan the studying of the experience of using the program-target method of budget planning in the EU countries, such as, Great Britain, France, Italy, and Germany.

The UK's budget policy is aimed at long-term regulation of the economy and social development, solving such important issues for societies as structural restructuring of the economy, solving problems of self-sufficiency of energy resources, keeping inflation at a substantiated level. At the same time, in the period up to the 1970s of the twentieth century, the policy in the sphere of the budget was aimed, mainly, at smoothing the cyclical fluctuations of the economy.

Considering the development of the program-target method in the UK, it is worth noting that the using of performance indicators for budget programs in this state is not regulated by law. However, starting in 1991, each ministry and department submits to the Parliament an annual report, which reflects the results achieved by it and the expected results in the next budget period. The state budget of Great Britain is formed on a medium-term basis for a period of three years; consists of a set of separate annual departmental programs based on which are the relevant state medium-term programs of economic development. The main objectives of the country's budget are the

financing of a wide range of the country's social and economic development.

France is one of the countries where medium-term planning has become the largest development. The transition to the application of the program-target method in the budget process of France began relatively recently, from the elaboration of the 2001 Draft Organic (Constitutional) Law on Public Finances (hereinafter referred to as the Law of LOLF (Loi Organique relative aux Lois des Finances), which entered into force on January 1, 2006, the LOLF Law introduced the concept of «effectiveness of budget expenditures» in France and consolidated the main principles of the program-target method. The objectives and performance indicators were formulated in the draft budget. In 2006 a fundamental change was made in budgeting: the transition from the logic of tracking expenditures to the logic of tracking the performance of public services [11].

The experience of France in organizing the training of new principles of the program-target method of employees involved in the implementation of its main elements can be useful to Uzbekistan. So, in 2003, in order to implement the budget reform within the Institute of State Management and Development of Economy (ISMDE), a separate department was set up, whose function was to support the reforms in the ministries. The Institute of State Management and Development of Economy has developed three stages of training for employees of ministries and departments that are involved in the implementation of the program-target method in any way. All three wave studies took place between 2003 and 2006 during the transition period preceding the implementation of the LOLF [11].

The world practice highlights the following key elements of program budgeting:

- a strategic planning of the activity of public authorities and its component - financial strategic planning;
- a medium-term budgeting, which defines certain time fiscal frameworks for optimal resource allocation in the medium-term program;
- a system for monitoring and evaluating budget programs and the results of their

performers (strategic plans are the basis for the latter) [1].

The experience of foreign countries testifies that there is no single methodology of program budgeting that can be applied in any country. This is due to the peculiarities of the budget system and the construction of the budget system of each country. However, the joint program-target budgeting is an organic combination of a clearly structured and substantive part of the program with the formation and using of organizational and financial mechanisms for its implementation, control over the implementation and achievement of the planned results.

The experience from different countries shows that program-targeted budgeting involves a fairly detailed periodic analysis of all programs that require significant human resources and often financial costs. In addition, programmatic budgeting is just one of the structural elements of a series of public administration reforms aimed at improving the performance of public institutions. It should be noted that the transition to medium-term budget planning in foreign countries took place gradually, took time and lasted on average from 5 till 10 years.

Most of the foreign countries that implemented budgeting techniques have done this in combination with other reforms for many years. The appropriate strategies were developed within the framework of a single strategic document for it (for example, a national strategy to be developed by the president or the government).

Foreign experience of using in practice the program-target approach in the budget process shows an increase in the responsibility of the spending units for achieving the final result, allows us to critically evaluate the spending of funds and to refuse unreasonable expenditures and to really assess the financial state of the state, due to a more complete picture of the resources available to it [11].

The conclusions. Given the foreign experience of introducing systemic changes in fiscal policy for Uzbekistan, we are confident that the application of the program-targeted method will help to make the best choice of the priority budget policy for the medium-term perspective and ensure the achievement of positive results with

the using of the budget funds. Improvement of the program-target method of expenditure planning will improve the quality of budget policy formulation of prioritization when allocating a limited amount of expenditures, increase the level of efficiency of using budget allocations, and facilitate streamlining of the activities of the main spending unit manager in executing budget programs. Strengthening the quality level of domestic budget policy, taking into account relevant world experience, will contribute to effective institutional transformation of social development.

References

1. Bugaj T.V., Galyuta A.A. Programno-cil'ovyj metod u byudzhetnomu procesi: zarubizhnyj dosvid i mozhlyvosti jogo vykorystannya v Ukrayini [Program-target method in the budget process: foreign experience and possibilities of its use in Uzbekistan] // Visnyk Zhytomyr'skogo texnologichnogo universytetu. – 2011. – No 3(57). – S. 206–210. – Bibliogr.: 8 nazv.
2. Bulgakova S.O., Baranovskij O.I., Kucher G.V. Byudzhetna sistema Ukrayiny ta Yevrosoyuzu [Budget system of Uzbekistan and the European Union] : monografiya ; M-vo osvity i nauky Ukrayiny ; za zag. red. A.A. Mazaraki. – K. : Kyiv. nacz. torg.-ekon. un-t, 2009. – 409 c. – Bibliogr.: s. 404-409.
3. Bjudzhetnyj kodeks Ukrai'ny [Budget Code of Uzbekistan] (2010). Vidomosti Verhovnoi Rady Ukrai'ny (VVR), 50-51. : <http://zakon5.rada.gov.ua/laws/show/2456-17>. (last access: 01.02.2017).
4. Zapatrina I.V., Lebeda T.B. Byudzhetna polityka sty'mulyuvannya ekonomichnogo zrostannya ta mexanizmy yiyi realizaciyi [Budget policy to stimulate economic growth and mechanisms for its implementation] // Finansy Ukrayiny. – 2006. – No 4. – S. 38–45. – Bibliogr.: 7 nazv.
5. Koncepciya zastosuvannya programno-cil'ovogo metodu v byudzhetnomu procesi [The concept of application of the program-target method in the budget

process], sxvalena rozporyadzhenniam Kabinetu Ministriv Ukrayiny` vid 14 veres. 2002 r. No 538-r. : <http://www.nau.kiev.ua>. (data zvernennya: 02.10.2017).

6. Ly`syak L.V. Vprovadzhennya programno-cil`ovogo metodu planuvannya vy`datkiv miscevy`x byudzhativ v Ukrayini [Implementation of the program-target method of planning of expenditures of local budgets in Uzbekistan] // Formuvannya ry`nkovoyi ekonomiky` v Ukrayini. – 2013. – Vy`p. 29. – Ch.2. – S. 3-9. – Bibliogr.: 14 nazv.

7. Myarkovs`ky`j A.I., Chugunov I.Ya. Byudzhetna polity`ka yak skladova social`no-ekonomichnogo rozvy`tku krayiny` [Budget policy as a component of socio-economic development of the country] // Visn. Ky`yiv. nacz. torg.-ekon un-tu. – 2010. – No 5. – S. 5–15. : http://nbuv.gov.ua/UJRN/Vknteu_2010_5_2. - Data zvernennya: 01.10.2017.

8. Ogon` Cz. G. Programno-cil`ovy`j metod ta efekty`vnist` byudzhetny`x program [The program-target method and efficiency of budget programs] // Finansy` Ukrayiny`. – 2009. – No 7. – S. 20–29. : http://nbuv.gov.ua/UJRN/Fu_2009_7_3. - Data zvernennya: 03.10.2017.

9. Osnovni napryamky` byudzhetnoyi polity`ky` na 2018-2020 roky` [The main directions of budget policy for 2018-2020 years]. : <https://www.minfin.gov.ua/uploads/redactor/files>. (data zvernennya 03.10.2017).

10. Fedosov V.M. Byudzhetny`j menedzhment [Budget Management] : pidruch. / Min-vo osvity` i nauky` Ukrayiny`, KNEU ; red. V.M. Fedosov. – K. : KNEU, 2004. – 864 s. – Bibliogr.: s. 855-863.

11. Xven` A.Yu. Vy`kory`stannya dosvidu byudzhetnogo menedzhmentu Yevropejs`kogo Soyuzu dlya Ukrayiny` [Using the experience of European Union budget management for Uzbekistan]. : <http://libfor.com/index.php?newsid=1859>. - Data zvernennya: 03.10.2017.

12. Chugunov I.Ya., Bry`zhan K.V. Byudzhetna polity`ka v umovax transformaciyi ekonomiky` [Budget policy in the context of transforming the economy]

// *Ekonomichny`j visny`k universy`tetu.* – 2017. – Vy`pusk 32/1. – S. 241-251.

Bibliogr.: 10 nazv.